

Filling the Gaps and Shifting Narratives: a digital methodology for collecting and analysing data for global histories¹

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Introduction

Historical research is centred around identifying and filling ‘gaps’ in historical narratives. Yet, as historical narratives are not produced equally and fairly, it can be difficult to move beyond established theories.² Without critical reflection on existing scholarship and its gaps, historical narratives will remain ‘single stories’³ from the perspective of dominant powers, at the expense of marginalised perspectives.⁴

With this concern in mind, we asked: in practice, **how can we approach conceptualising gaps in scholarship, and what steps can we take to fill these gaps up?** We work with the idea that gaps – or absences or silences – are sites of greater opportunity, instead of pitfalls to be ignored.⁵

We present a practical digital methodology that addresses this representation concern in two parts: 1) identifying absent and/or underrepresented narratives and 2) addressing this inequality. It encourages researchers to approach their research fields critically and explore scholarly fields beyond their own. The methodology is a response to the urgent need for rethinking established yet outdated concepts within historiography – moving away from paradigmatic narratives and viewing them through post-colonial, transnational, and global lenses. The use of digital technologies aids us in this pursuit: our digital approach produces a dynamic, inclusive, accessible, and democratic overview of scholarship in the form of an annotated bibliography. Outlined here are our key goals within this methodology:

- **Dynamic:** ever-expanding, regularly updating, routinely reflected upon.

¹ We thank the reviewers of DH Benelux 2025 for their feedback on our submitted abstract.

² Trouillot, Michel-Rolph. *Silencing the Past: Power and the Production of History*. Boston, Massachusetts: Beacon Press, 1995.

³ Adichie, Chimamanda Ngozi. *The Danger of a Single Story*, 2009.

https://www.ted.com/talks/chimamanda_ngozi_adichie_the_danger_of_a_single_story.

⁴ With ‘marginalised perspectives’, we refer to perspectives and narratives systematically not included in established historiography centralised in western Europe and North America. See also Mak, Bonnie. “Archaeology of a Digitization.” *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* 65, no. 8 (2014): 1515–26. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23061>.

⁵ Sherman, Jihan, Romi Morrison, Lauren Klein, and Daniela Rosner. “The Power of Absence: Thinking with Archival Theory in Algorithmic Design.” In *Designing Interactive Systems Conference*, 214–23. IT University of Copenhagen Denmark: ACM, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3643834.3660690>.

- **Inclusive aims:** includes scholarship outside of direct scope of traditional historiography, includes non-English language sources, includes (more) scholars from the Global South.
- **Accessible:** accessible from all over the world (granted that there is a stable internet infrastructure), available to researchers and the broader public.
- **Democratic:** anyone can contribute to the overview.

Global Labour History and Collective Labour Action

We explore our digital methodology by situating it within the field of Global Labour History, based on our work on the HUB Global Labour Conflicts project, situated at the International Institute of Social History in Amsterdam.⁶ Global Labour History, a field (or rather, methodology) of history, is concerned with centring the mobility of people and goods, viewing historic processes of work as transcending national borders and boundaries.⁷ In addition to transcending borders, Global Labour History is the study of labour relations that seeks to go beyond traditional understandings and binaries of labour: “It concerns the history of all those people who through their work have built our modern world - not only wage labourers, but also chattel slaves, sharecroppers, housewives, the self-employed, and many other groups. It focuses on the labour relations of these people, as individuals but also as members of households, networks and other contexts.”⁸

While there have been many valuable contributions in Global Labour History, shifting narratives beyond Eurocentric biases, it remains difficult to map key conceptual and methodological insights from this relatively new field of history. This is specifically the case for perspectives on collective labour action (CLA). Expanding beyond traditional Western, modern, and strike-centred frameworks, the HUB Global Labour Conflicts project encompasses diverse forms of collective action undertaken in a labour context by a variety of actors, across varied geographies and historical periods.⁹ Our research methodology resulted in an overview of the developments within scholarship that touches upon collective labour action, using digital methods to map and analyse vast amounts of literature, ultimately revealing new insights about the state of research.

⁶ Project-page HUB Global Labour Conflicts: <https://iisg.amsterdam/en/blog/hub-global-labour-conflicts>.

⁷ Linden, Marcel van der. *Workers of the World: Essays toward a Global Labor History*. Brill, 2008. <https://brill.com/view/title/14554>; Eckert, Andreas. *Global Histories of Work*. De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110437201>; Sebastian Conrad, *What is Global History?* (Princeton 2016) 5.

⁸ International Institute of Social History, research projects “Global Labour History” blog, <https://iisg.amsterdam/en/research/projects/global-labour-history>. Accessed 17/12/2024.

⁹ Kösters, R., Simpson, C., & Aurich, J. (2023). Workers’ Resistance across Time and Space: Presenting the Hub Global Labour Conflicts. *TSEG - The Low Countries Journal of Social and Economic History*, 20(2). <https://doi.org/10.52024/tseg.14505>.

Digital Methodology: identifying and addressing *terra incognita*

As is the case with many tricky concepts, literature on all forms of labour-related collective actions is diverse, diffuse and spans many different fields of research. In order to map the state of scholarship, the digital workflow we developed in the context of CLA follows four main steps: collect, categorise, analyse, and compare. These steps allow for systematic categorisation of existing literature and the creation of a database classified by content and scope.

Figure 1: *Digital methodology workflow*

Figure 1 shows the general workflow we developed, in which we collected and categorised literature, and outlined notable findings. First, we compiled an extensive list of literature on (potential) collective labour actions (a), which we then added to an Excel and Zotero database in order to broadly categorise the readings (b). From this list we mapped the literature (creating graphs to visualise the results) and identified gaps (c). Subsequently, we compiled clusters by identifying areas of the literature that were thematically related (d) with the aim of analysing them together (e) and writing a summary (f) that would help to expand

our theoretical and conceptual understanding of the state of the art in research on CLA. These summaries were written in the programme Obsidian, with the ultimate aim of making them open access. While the creation of categories (to classify the literature) and templates (to analyse the literature) helped to form a systematic approach, we made sure to maintain a feedback loop (3-5) through which we could adapt our workflow to accommodate new findings and perspectives. This further demonstrates the democratic nature of this process - every step was subject to (both internal and external) feedback and revision to remain a reflexive approach.

Results

Our collection of over 600 readings uncovers biases the established scholarship holds with regards to CLA. Figure 2 shows that the majority of the literature has a modernist focus, as most studies are concerned with historical events taking place between 1800 and 2000. Concurrently, we see spikes in readings on striking and organising. This coincides with the more commonly accepted notion that while physical and armed resistance decreased around the emergence of the industrial revolution in Europe, striking and organising became common forms of resistance for industrial workers. This Eurocentric notion is further confirmed by Figure 3, which shows that the collected literature is heavily focussed on Western contexts. Yet, Figure 4 crucially shows that this tide is changing, and that scholarship more recently has focussed increasingly on Global South and global contexts.

To start filling in these gaps, we focus on cluster analysis. From the disparate readings we have collected and categorised in our database, we cluster together selections of literature that we believe are insightful to be read alongside each other. These clusters are based on the underrepresented actions, actors, temporal and/or geographical factors these reading may have in common. We then review these clusters, thereby shedding light on the state of research and gaps therein. To illustrate the centrality of underrepresented contexts, the cluster reviews we have written until now explore (among others) the act of silence as a form of collective labour action, female Asian workers' resistance, early modern resistance to penal labour by convicts in the Danish-Norwegian Empire, and resistance against enslavement in the West-African hinterlands.

Bringing these clusters together enables us to bring together different perspectives for the first time. For example, we see how female labourers, both in the domestic sphere and the industrial sphere, in South America and Asia, relied on female communities in order to resist

their labour situation.¹⁰ This opens up the view that communities that are hitherto historiographically separated from labour contexts can play a crucial role in labour resistance and shows how domestic labour should come under attention from historians who have traditionally placed industrial work at centre stage. Bringing together different established historiographies while centring underrepresented categories sheds light on biases and gaps in the state of research and allows us to map the *terra incognita* between the established fields.

These clusters are currently in the process of being made publicly available, together with our bibliography. We aim for these resources to become open and dynamic: all researchers, no matter in what phase of their study or career, are invited to make use of and contribute to this historiographical database – from gathering relevant readings to writing cluster reports on the fields that interest them. We also created a list of attributes that are important to consider when researching CLA. These attributes will help future researchers to go beyond presupposed imaginations of what is understood under ‘collective’, ‘labour’, and ‘action’. Key attributes we have identified are intentionality, temporality, social and spatial spheres of action, collectivity, and actors and their roles.

We have also explored options for future primary source research on resistance to take our first steps in filling up the gaps we found. Specifically, following from underrepresented categories we found while gathering and reviewing literature, we scoured primary source material for terms that are not conventionally used in the context of, and thought about as, labour resistance. Thus, we explored references to desertion and amok in Dutch-language newspapers published in 1700-1900. This resulted in two data-publications with corresponding data-reviews and historiographical reports.¹¹ We found that our method leads to new and fruitful avenues of research into labour history, discovering histories that are barely touched upon in our field.

Conclusion

¹⁰ For example, see: Matsumura, Wendy. “More than the ‘Wife Corps’: Female Tenant Farmer Struggle in 1920s Japan.” *International Labor and Working-Class History* 91 (2017): 127–55. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0147547916000302>; Baugh-Helton, Tiffany. “They Came to Scoff, But Stayed to Peel Onions: Reproductive Labor and Collective Action in the 1936–1937 Flint Sit-Down Strike.” *Journal of Women’s History* 33, no. 1 (2021): 61–84. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jowh.2021.0003>; Allman, Jean Marie. “*I Will Not Eat Stone*”: *A Women’s History of Colonial Asante*. Heinemann, 2000. <https://hdl.handle.net/2027/heb02548.0001.001>.

¹¹ Läufer, Josephine; Aurich, Jens, 2024, "Desertion Events in 19th Century Dutch Newspapers", <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/D6OXZ9>, IISH Data Collection, V3; Van Kasteel, Teun; Aurich, Jens, 2024, "Amok Events in 19th Century Dutch Newspapers", <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/OWVWVT>, IISH Data Collection, V4.

This abstract argues for a systematic methodology, aided by digital tools, to critically identify and redress gaps within established fields of historiography. While moving away from Eurocentric narratives more broadly requires addressing structural issues within academia, like breaking down language and institutional access barriers, our digital methodology provides a first step in identifying pressing gaps within scholarship, illustrated by our work on collective labour action. We developed strategies for data collection to attempt to fill some of these gaps, with the ultimate goal of creating a global research Collaboratory for this area of research.

Figure 2: Literature divided by century of focus and most prominent types of CLA

World Map showing Publications by Region

Figure 3: Publications by region

Figure 4: *Publications on CLA 1940-2024 and their topic regions*